

Understanding the Kinetic Marketplaces: A Case of Ahmedabad

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Submitted By

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Executive Summary

This research shall focus on integrating the kinetic nature of marketplaces. For the purpose of this study two sites Manek chowk and Bhadra plaza has been studied. Both sites are present in the old city of Ahmedabad.

These marketplaces, historically known as 'bazaars,' have evolved naturally alongside communities and are frequently more well-known for their iconic position and urban character. Many of our historic towns grew out of a strong economic grasp and eventually expanded into civilizations with markets spread across the city's environment.

Bazaars subsequently legitimate commercial land use inside municipal plans when the fundamental essence and character are detrimental to urban growth. With the emergence of malls and supermarkets, the relevance of these market streets has declined. With the move from public to private that has happened throughout history, bazaars have been turned into formal stores that are indoor common places. We are losing a significant portion of our urban life as a result of this change. Our temporary markets' organic and spreading character creates an exchanging ground for social, economic, and cultural aspects that bring energy to the location.

At this period of transition in the city's growth, I believe that we should analyse and strengthen the mobile and temporary characteristics of marketplaces. It is vital to build with these temporal dimensions in mind, to provide such public space flexibility and elasticity, and to allow a wide range of activities over a wide range of time periods. Today's public space designs are generally prescriptive and minimize conflict, but in a densely populated and multicultural city like Ahmedabad, spaces that foster a varied mix of people and activities are required. As a result, there is a strong desire to investigate these market areas before they vanish.

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Chapter - 1 Introduction

1.1 Understanding Static and Kinetic

Indian cities or urban spaces are made up of many components that share the same physical space (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). These elements can be categorized into two parts: The Formal or Static City and The Dynamic or Kinetic city; two completely distinct worlds that coexist in the same urban environment (Mehotra, *Learning from Mumbai*, 2003).

It is necessary to understand what static and kinetic imply in this context in order to investigate how these two distinct worlds interact with each other and co-exist in the same physical setting (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018). Nevertheless, the terms static and kinetic can be defined in different settings; for the sake of this research, we will use the definitions provided by Rahul Mehotra in his book "*The Kinetic City*."

1.1.1 Static

Made of more permanent materials such as concrete, steel, and brick having a sense of permanence (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). It is represented as a two-dimensional entity on traditional city maps and is enormous in scale and depends on the architecture and monumental in its presence (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018). In other words, static refers to the city's built entity, which is typically associated with permanence (Mehrotra, *Negotiating The Static and Kinetic Cities the Emergent Urbanism of Mumbai*, 2008).

While the static predominantly portrays the built form, it may be enlarged to include other city elements that, although permanent in nature, are not always built (Dwivedi & Mehotra, 2010). Trees and landforms, for example, are part of a static entity but they would not be classified as built form; rather, they showed a natural form of the city (Dwivedi & Mehotra, 2010). The static mainly reflects the architectural characteristics of the city, but fails to communicate the complete picture of the city (Mehotra, Vora, Hoskote, & Mehta, 2021).

1.1.2 Kinetic

However, the Kinetic city is a city in motion — a three-dimensional construction of incremental development that is intelligible as a two-dimensional entity (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018). The Kinetic City is temporary in nature and structure made of recycled materials such as plastic sheets, scrap metal, canvas, and discarded wood. It is constantly evolving and reinventing itself (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). Architecture is no longer the spectacular of the city in the dynamic city; rather, processions and festivals create its image and remembrance,

and the city's inherent expression is temporal in nature, in constant flux (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). Kinetic City is indigenous urbanism that has its particular 'local' logic (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018).

The Kinetic City presents an engaging vision that has the potential to help people better understand the blurred borders of modern urbanism and the shifting roles of people and spaces in urban life (Mehrotra, *Negotiating The Static and Kinetic Cities the Emergent Urbanism of Mumbai*, 2008). It is not always a poor city, as most images suggest; rather, it is a temporal articulation and occupancy of space that not only generates a richer perception of spatial occupation but also illustrates how spatial limitations are extended to incorporate formally unimagined uses within dense urban settings (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018).

1.1.3 Co-existence

The presence of two worlds in the same environment implies the accommodation and overlap of varied uses, perceptions, and physical forms (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018). In an urban setting charged with the duality of permanence and rapid flux, there are no comprehensive solutions (Mehotra & Vera, *The Architectural Review*, 2018). Opposing characteristics must be harmonized as valid at the same time. Let's look at an example to further understand and illustrate the coexistence of static and kinetic.

The phenomena of bazaars in the Victorian arcades of Mumbai's Historic District, the old Fort Area, is representative of this possible negotiation between the Static and Kinetic City (Dwivedi & Mehotra, 2010). The arcades were originally used for two purposes; first created spatial mediation between the building and the street and second, the arcades were a great solution to the climatic conditions of Bombay (Mehotra, Vora, Hoskote, & Mehta, 2021). They provided a buffer zone between pedestrians and the intense heat and rain (Dwivedi & Mehotra, 2010). With the informal bazaar dominating the arcade now, the arcade's original purpose is challenged (Mehotra, Vora, Hoskote, & Mehta, 2021).

1.2 Background

According to Carr, Streets are the most "public": they are responsive, accessible, diverse, democratic and multipurpose (Deore, Prithvi; Lathia, Saumya;, 2019). As per Brower's perspective; In all civilizations, streets have been the most widely used public space, with commercial streets and bazaars being the most popular (Deore, Prithvi; Lathia, Saumya;, 2019).

Many of our historic towns grew out of a strong economic grasp and eventually expanded into civilizations with markets spread across the city's environment (Paisana, 2018). As a result of the silk routes that emerged in the old precincts of Hyderabad, markets have emerged (Paisana, 2018). These marketplaces, historically known as 'bazaars,' have evolved naturally alongside communities and are

frequently more well-known for their iconic position and urban character (Paisana, 2018).

Bazaars subsequently legitimate commercial land use inside municipal plans when the fundamental essence and character are detrimental to urban growth (Paisana, 2018). With the emergence of malls and supermarkets, the relevance of these market streets has declined (Paisana, 2018). With the move from public to private that has happened throughout history, bazaars have been turned into formal stores that are indoor common places (Paisana, 2018). We are losing a significant portion of our urban life as a result of this change (Paisana, 2018). Our temporary markets' organic and spreading character creates an exchanging ground for social, economic, and cultural aspects that bring energy to the location (Paisana, 2018).

Markets and public places should be examined and strengthened in terms of their mobile and temporary dimensions (Paisana, 2018). It is vital to build with these temporal dimensions in mind in order to deliver flexibility and elasticity to these public spaces and to allow a wide range of activities throughout a diverse time span (Paisana, 2018). Today's public space design is frequently prescriptive and avoids conflicts, yet in a congested environment, it is vital to build areas that foster a dynamic mix of people and activities (Paisana, 2018). As a result, there is a strong desire to investigate these market areas before they vanish (Paisana, 2018).

1.3 Overview of thesis

1.3.1 Research questions

1. What are the temporary, flexible and informal activities that give a dynamic character to the urban marketplace?
2. How urban market spaces accommodate various transformations happening throughout the day.

1.3.2 Aim

The research shall focus on integrating the kinetic nature of marketplaces.

1.3.3 Objectives

1. To document and present the temporary, flexible and informal activities.
2. To study the role of kinetic elements in transforming the marketplace.
3. Formulate a set of ideas/parameters that need to be considered before designing the marketplaces at the urban planning level.

1.3.4 Key words

1. Kinetic
2. Static
3. Market places
4. Adaptability of Spaces
5. Flexibility

1.3.5 Rationale for intervention

The design of today's marketplaces is typically prescriptive and minimizes disputes, yet in a congested environment, it is critical to creating places that support a dynamic mix of people and activities. It is critical to design with these temporal dimensions in mind in order to provide these markets flexibility and elasticity and to allow a wide range of activities across the time. Street markets are perceived as a commercialization of public space, a resource that is scarce in the city, and they are disputed territory. As a result, at this period of transition in the city's growth, I believe that we should analyse and strengthen the mobile and temporary characteristics of marketplaces. It is vital to build with these temporal dimensions in mind, to provide such public space flexibility and elasticity, and to allow a wide range of activities over a wide range of time periods. Today's public space designs are generally prescriptive and minimize conflict, but in a densely populated and multicultural city like Ahmedabad, spaces that foster a varied mix of people and activities are required. As a result, there is a tremendous urge to research these marketplaces before they disappear.

1.3.6 Scope and limitations

Scope

1. The research will focus on two major city level markets, which are temporal in nature in the city of Ahmedabad as it has been operating since the establishment of the early settlement.
2. Two marketplaces Bhadra plaza market and Manek chowk have been taken into consideration for the study. Historically, Manek Chowk precinct has been the commercial centre while Bhadra plaza served as the royal space for the public. Today, both the Bhadra Plaza and Manek Chowk serve as retail public spaces for domestic and festival shopping for people from in and around Ahmedabad. At the end of the study list of parameters has been identified which will be helpful in new market street design.

Limitations

1. The study only focuses on city level marketplaces and does not include other types of markets like neighbourhood markets.
2. Due to Covid -19 outbreak there might be some restrictions or changes in the nature of the market which might not be visible.

1.3.7 Research Framework

Research framework is divided into six parts. First part is to identify and study the kinetic and static elements of the marketplace. Next stage is to study how these marketplaces are function. After that analysis of temporal activities that plays an important role to marketplaces has been analysed. The further stage is to study changes that takes place in marketplace throughout the day which makes it kinetic. After studying and analysing all these factors final analysis and findings has been derived and then the set of ideas that needs to be consider before designing the marketplace has been formulate.

Figure 1 – Research framework

1.3.8 Research Structure

This thesis comprises six chapters which includes introduction, literature study, Site Selection and Site context, Data collection tools and techniques, field study and data analysis and conclusion chapter.

The chapter one is Introduction that includes background, Research questions, aim, objectives, Key words, rationale for intervention, scope and limitations, methodological approach, research framework and schedule of the thesis.

Chapter two consists of a Literature Review which includes four subchapters named Definition of Time, The Temporal Dimension, Understanding the Kinetic, Temporal Dimensions of Public Space and Framework of Analysis.

Chapter three is site selection and site context which explains how the specific sites have been selected. It also includes the context of the site.

Chapter four is focused on data collection tools and techniques. It explains how different data has been captured.

Chapter five comprises the analysed data of the site visit.

The chapter six is conclusion, which includes what was the study about, key findings, way forward and the concluding statement.

Chapter - 2 Literature Studies

2.1 Definition of Time

Time is defined as the measurable duration of an occurrence from the past through the present to the future, which is an irreversible process of human evolution. The temporal activity differs and changes depending on the time frame. Time, as a dimensional component that influences the link between temporal activity and the permanence of places, is divided into two terms: long time-period and short time-period. Long periods of time involve the process in years or decades; short periods of time involve the procedure in a day, distinguishing between the morning, afternoon, and night. It is critical to integrate time as a factor in design in order to adapt to the present community's quick changes. In this study, I will investigate how to use time as an element in the design process in order to facilitate temporal activities.

2.2 The Temporal Dimension

Kevin Lynch suggests: “we can observe the effect of time on space in two ways: first is rhythmic repetition, or breathing, sleeping, walking, and cycles of the sun, moon, and seasons and second is progressive and irreversible change, or growth and decay, which are two ways time affects space” (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010).

2.2.1 Time Cycle

The primary time cycles are based on natural cycles (our bodily cycles). The utilization of urban space varies according to the cycles of day, night, and season. The urban environment is viewed and utilized differently at different times of the day and night, and users change according to the shifting time cycle (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). To create useful, functional, and exciting urban spaces, urban designers must be aware of these cycles. Otherwise, the urban environment begins to deteriorate. The major goal is to a cycle of time Activities are temporary in both place and time (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010).

The various seasons also act as a platform for activity cycles (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). Even at midday in northern temperate climates during the winter, for example, the sun is low in the sky. The days are usually cloudy, rainy, windy, and chilly. People should only utilize public areas when absolutely essential (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). In the spring, trees begin to grow leaves, and people begin to stay in urban areas, resting in the warmth of the sun (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). In the summer, the trees are in full bloom, the sun is high in the sky, the days are long and sunny, and people choose to spend more time in cities (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). The leaves become beautiful reds and browns in the autumn and finally fall off the trees. People may gather in urban spaces to take advantage of the last rays of sunlight before the arrival of winter (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010).

2.2.2 Time Management of Public spaces

Mixed-use developments have traditionally been promoted on the grounds that they increase the amount of life and activity in a specific area. Activity must be considered in terms of time as well. Urban designers must understand activity patterns and how to inspire activities at different times of day (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). The time of activities must be regulated. Activities may be restricted at specific periods to avoid conflicts, separated in time to reduce congestion, or brought together in time to allow connections and a suitable density of usage (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010).

Densely populated urban areas allow complementary activities to intersect in space and interrelate complexly, opposing the limited temporal specialization that splits and compartmentalizes activities (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). While the influx and flow of people going about their daily business frequently spontaneously animates public space, this may also be fostered by intentional programs encouraging people to come, use, and stay in urban settings (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). Programs often include a diverse range of events and activities. As a result, as more people visit an area to observe what's going on, urban vibrancy is boosted further, and the public realm becomes more active by having more people on the streets and in cafes, etc (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010).

2.2.3 The March of Time

We know that time has passed not just through the use of the repeating rhythms of time, but also through signs of constant and irreversible change (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). In a way, the past is permanent while the future is limitless. While we may wish to return to the city we knew as children or relive a happy memory, we are unable to do so (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). This is the never-ending "march of time." The urban environment is constantly and inevitably evolving. Environments and structures are transformed and remade by technical, economic, social, and cultural change from the initial design sketch to the last destruction (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). A structure or other feature of the built environment from a specific era and kind tends to be a carrier of the spirit of its era (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010). City life can be read as an intricate, multi-layered text, as a narrative of signs and symbols enclosing a biography of urban change (Carmona, Tiesdell, Heath, & Oc, 2010).

2.3 Importance the Kinetic

2.3.1 Cities within a city

Cities in South Asia are defined by visual and physical contrasts that combine to create a landscape of extraordinary diversity (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). Traditionally, especially during the period of British occupation, the multiple worlds functioning inside these cities – whether economic, social, or cultural – inhabited different locations and followed different norms (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). The goal of their division was to maximize control while minimizing friction between two frequently contradictory cultures (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013).

Today, nevertheless, these worlds share the same place, but they interpret and utilize it in quite different ways (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). During the latter part of the twentieth century, massive waves of troubled rural migration converged to form a single, but diverse entity (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). This, along with an insufficient supply of urban land and a lack of new urban centers, resulted in exceptionally high densities in existing cities. The advent of a post-industrial, service-based economy has increased the interweaving of multiple worlds inside the same place (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013).

These entities are now the Static and Kinetic components of a city. What began as a control model with clear divisions of function and usage has evolved into a space where such distinctions are blurred (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). Cities within cities now exist as a single entity. They work together to form a whole.

2.3.2 Bazaar urbanism

Today, however, these worlds share the same place, but they interpret and utilise it in quite different ways (Mehotra, Vora, Hoskote, & Mehta, 2021). During the latter part of the twentieth century, massive waves of troubled rural migration converged to form a single, but diverse entity (Mehrotra, *Negotiating The Static and Kinetic Cities the Emergent Urbanism of Mumbai*, 2008). This, along with an insufficient supply of urban land and a lack of new urban centres, resulted in exceptionally high densities in existing cities (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). With the advent of a post-industrial, service-based economy, the interconnection of multiple worlds inside the same area has become even greater (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013).

Cities in India have become crucial places for negotiation between elite and subaltern cultures in this post-industrial era (Mehrotra, *Negotiating The Static and Kinetic Cities the Emergent Urbanism of Mumbai*, 2008). In a post-industrial economy, the new relationships between social classes are quite different from those that existed in state-controlled economies (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). The economic fragmentation in service and manufacturing sectors has resulted in a new, bazaar-like urbanism that has weaved its presence across the

whole urban environment (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013) . This is an urbanization built by individuals outside the elite boundaries of the state's formal modernity (Mehotra, Vora, Hoskote, & Mehta, 2021). It is a 'pirate' modernism that must avoid the city's regulations merely to live, with no purposeful attempt to build a counterculture (Mehrotra, *Negotiating The Static and Kinetic Cities the Emergent Urbanism of Mumbai*, 2008). With the state's withdrawal, the domain of the 'everyday' is where economic and cultural issues are articulated (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013). These common areas have been largely ignored from cultural discourses on globalization, which have focused on the city's elite domains of production (Mehrotra, *The static and the kinetic*, 2013).

2.3.3 The grand adjustment

The Kinetic City offers a powerful vision that allows us to better comprehend the blurring borders of modern urbanism as well as the shifting roles of people and spaces in urban life (Mehotra, *Mumbai - Kinetic City*, 2018). The increased attention of global flows has reinforced social class inequities and regional divides (Mehrotra, *The architectural wonder of impermanent city* , 2019). In such a situation, an architecture or urbanism of equality in an increasingly inequitable economic state necessitates a deeper research to locate a diverse variety of sites to recognize and celebrate the cultures of individuals excluded from global flows (Mehrotra, *The architectural wonder of impermanent city* , 2019). These are not always found in the formal construction of architecture; rather, they frequently contradict it (Mehotra, *Mumbai - Kinetic City*, 2018). The concept of a city in this context is an elastic urban condition—not a great vision, but a "grand adjustment" (Mehrotra, *The architectural wonder of impermanent city* , 2019).

2.4 Temporal Dimensions of Public Space

2.4.1 Temporality and market spaces

According to an example from Paisano's research, "Temporal Dimensions of Public Space: The Case of Vendors and Markets in Ahmedabad," before the redesigning of Bhadra plaza, there was a market with over 900 vendors that drew visitors from all over the city (Paisana, 2018). They offered a wide range of items and food at reasonable prices, and they were the main reason people came to this public place. The revival of Bhadra required a redesign of its public area that only included a portion of the market, but after a few months, all of the vendors returned to sell here and adapted their informal selling to the new space structure (Paisana, 2018). This brings up the question of how designers can recognize informal, flexible, mobile, and transitory activities and incorporate them into urban design and planning processes (Paisana, 2018).

The first step, crucially, would be to recognise their presence in the city and to explore and understand their spatial arrangement processes (Paisana, 2018). Street

vendors and their vending structures determine the character of public space in addition to contributing to the urban economy by producing jobs and supplying accessible items to the urban areas (Paisana, 2018). Stalls, carts, and product displays provide areas for economic and social interactions, and their placement organizes and defines how people utilize open space (Paisana, 2018). For example, the shade systems employed on vending buildings make the places surrounding them more comfortable to walk around on a bright day (temperatures in Ahmedabad often reach 50o Celsius). They also play a vital role in street safety, serving as informal eyes on the street (Paisana, 2018).

Since these vending structures are temporary, non-permanent, and perceived informal, they are frequently neglected in urban planning and design choices (Paisana, 2018). Ahmedabad's urban fabric has evolved dramatically in recent years, thanks to massive infrastructural projects including the BRT, metro, and riverside reconstruction, as well as beautification initiatives such as Kankaria Lake and Bhadra Square (Paisana, 2018). These kinds of projects are presently one of the leading causes of street vendor evictions from public spaces (Paisana, 2018).

2.4.2 Temporal Market - A Neutral Ground for Sociability

When public places in cities seem dynamic, it gives the city a particular character; and this character gives identity to the city (Katake, 2021). The variety and diversity of temporal marketplaces are fascinating. The way street vendors organize their sales in the smallest amount of area along the street, sidewalks, public spaces, and so on is remarkable. To exhibit their sale, they encroach on built structure, sometimes even private in nature (footpaths, otlas, steps, compound walls, railing of traffic islands, bridges, areas beneath skywalks or flyovers, etc.). Streets and sidewalks play a vital part in creating an active public realm in public areas. Streets play a vital role in urban fabric not only for transportation but also for socio-cultural and economic creation (Katake, 2021). The concept of the temporal market is eye-catching. The sellers utilize the area for a set length of time before returning it to the city for other activities (Katake, 2021). An active public realm is created by the vibrancy of temporality in public areas. Street vendors attempt to strategically organize their items. For example, they choose the location in which to display their items, such as nodes, streets, and squares, in order to catch the public's attention (Katake, 2021). The market area is not only for the exchange of products, but also for socializing and the creation of an inclusive atmosphere (Katake, 2021). These points are undoubtedly lacking in the digital retail sector, which is why our traditional Indian markets, or bazaars, play such an important role in the current online retail era (Katake, 2021)!

2.4.3 Local Body's Overlook of Temporal Marketplaces

Niketa Suresh Katake discusses the temporary market at Goda ghat, which is located in the heart of Nashik (Katake, 2021). The area's religious activities, rituals, leisure activities, and marketplace contribute to a dynamic and vibrant public domain. The

town's urban fabric, major hubs of the city, tourist appealing sites, historic formal market, and efficient public and private transit system are some of the reasons for the precinct's thriving temporal market (Katake, 2021). The majority of street vendors share space with formal shops that are exposed to the air and operate freely, and some sellers organize themselves with formal marketplaces (Katake, 2021). Street sellers strategically organize their items and maximize the area by employing light and inexpensive materials for their temporary creations (Katake, 2021).

After examining the temporal market using the three factors identity, activity, and physical features, it is clear that the temporal market's activity is significant in this location since it has a strong social, cultural, and economic character (Katake, 2021). Niketa Suresh Katake stated: "The state authority's attempt to relocate the temporary market will limit the city's dynamic public domain and cause the city to lose its character" (Katake, 2021). The area will appear inactive, monotonous, and transport oriented. It will encourage robbery and other problems that might make the city dangerous. Street sellers are an integral aspect of the city. Rather than properly planning temporal space and providing adequate services to street vendors, our state and local governments are continually attempting to push them, hassle them, and penalize them by citing causes like disorder, congestion, and so on. Congestion and disruption are unavoidable, but forcing them to the outskirts and limiting their ability to sell may result in another squatter scenario (Katake, 2021). The problems with temporary street markets are substantial and require specific management.

Niketa Suresh Katake concluded that Planners and designers may make significant contributions to our communal and inclusive well-being through market spaces by reserving some areas for temporary markets based on the needs of street sellers, as opposed to large structures (Katake, 2021). Allow and expand the area for the time-bound hawker zone above the No hawker zone. Street vendors and temporary markets are a part of the city; they give the locale, and occasionally the city, its personality (Katake, 2021). We must sustain our ancient market method, known as Bazaar in the local tongue.

2.5 Framework of Analysis

Elements of Market Streets

Static Elements

1. Buildings
2. Building Frontages
3. Footpaths
4. Roads
5. Parking slots
6. Bus/ Auto stops

7. Landscape
8. Signboards
9. Existing interaction places

Kinetic Elements

1. Traffic Pattern
2. Pedestrian movement
3. Street vendors and hawkers
4. Temporary vending infrastructure
5. Human interactions
6. Celebration of festivals

co-existence

No.	Parameters of Studying Great Street	Elaborate the Parameters
1.	Place for people to walk with some leisure	People should be able to have a great experience (on foot) and meet new people while strengthening the city/town culture.
2.	Physical comfort	The street must be comfortable, at least in their own surroundings. This provides a measure of physical comfort for the users.
3.	Definition (Human sensitive scale)	The definition of a street should be human-friendly, with a ratio (width: height) or sensitive proportions to human size that can improve the dynamic character of the street while experiencing it.
4.	Qualities that engages the eyes	Every great street has elements or features that attract a person's attention during his or her journey. This street comes to life thanks to architectural components, movements, light and shadows, and so on.
5.	Transparency	Each street has a different amount of transparency due to the street and adjacent configurations. This is heavily influenced by the community and the sort of activities that take place in it.
6.	Maintenance	It is more than just keeping things clean

		and in excellent condition, but it also includes the use of materials that are comparatively easy to maintain.
7.	Quality of construction and design	Nothing compares to the excellent or bad quality of a building or design; it's always about utilizing the appropriate materials in the right place to establish the good quality of the built environment for the street.

2.6 Case Studies

2.6.1 The Campo Square, Italy

It is a completely different open public place in terms of function, having been transformed from a packed road to a crowded public space with people. The Campo Square in Siena, Italy, is a one-of-a-kind square whose form is shaped by the surrounding structures. For a long time, Campo Square served as a venue for fairs and markets. After a few years, the Campo Square became a venue for all major events, such as buffalo and bull races, due to its considerable size to accommodate the whole community. The Campo square, as a unique gathering area, continues to be an important civic and social focus for the towns today. The link between public places and temporal activities is both long and short term, depending on the situation. The Campo Square is in a long-term state because of modifications that are noticeable only after years or decades.

Figure 2 - Campo Square, Italy in ancient time

Source: 2 <https://www.hellomonaco.com/the-riviera/italian-riviera/italian-holidays-pisa-siena-florence-portovenere-and-montecatini/>

Figure 3 - Campo Square, Italy nowadays

Source: 1 <https://www.itinari.com/de/siena-s-piazza-del-campo-6r6e>

2.6.2 Jalan Alor Street, Quall Lumpur

Jalan Alor, a typical roadway in Kuala Lumpur's city centre that operated as a conduit for vehicles to travel about. There are various food vendors along the road's stores during the day: Beginning about Opm, food booths convert the entire street into a hawker hub known for its local cuisine. Depending on the situation, the interaction between public places and temporal activities is both long and short term. The temporal aspect of Jalan Alor is in a short-term condition, as the changes noticeable in a day.

Figure 5 - Jalan Alor street during day

Source: 4 <https://everybodyhatesatourist.net/layover-kuala-lumpur-jalan-alor-islamic-arts-museum-malaysia/>

Figure 4 - - Jalan Alor street during night

Source: 3 <https://livein.com/blog/my/student-en-tune-hotels-downtown-kl-student-special/>

2.6.3 Town hall, Mumbai

Every year on August 15, India's Independence Day, celebrations hosted in Mumbai's Town Hall demonstrate the Kinetic City's transformational power. The Public Works Department (PWD) subverts the meaning and symbolism of the architecture by reconfiguring the design of this classical edifice for an annual ceremony in which the Governor of the State addresses the citizenry. The PWD builds a structure, similar to a large porch, that attaches to the building and protects it from monsoon rains. Built overnight in bamboo and fabric, the decorative trim and other ornamental features graft a local and maybe traditional sense onto this classical building, temporarily changing the design.

Figure 6 - Town hall, Mumbai before celebration

Figure 7 - Town hall, Mumbai during celebration

2.6.4 Streets of Kolkata during the festival

The city is transformed during the Durga Puja, when widely dispersed population groups assemble in select areas around Kolkata for six days and nights to honour the goddess Durga. Alleyways and streets are transformed by the presence of pandals, which are temporary structures built to honour the goddess. The urban fabric becomes more permeable, enabling for the formation of new places of worship, prayer, and celebration. Meaningful neighbourhood connections and a feeling of community emerge, reuniting the city's generally dispersed population into distinct clusters of intense social interaction organised by area. Kolkata's identity transforms, obliterating social divides and hierarchies in a richly textured landscape of convergent, small-scale, and profound religious practises. The elaborate simulation of monuments and landscapes, ranging from architectural copies of temples to village complexes surrounded by artificial reconstructions of natural landscapes, takes months of planning and work on the part of both the public and private sectors, as well as the general public. Many wonderfully carved gods and goddesses are constructed in homes, studios, and ateliers across the city. The idols are immersed in a river, sea, or tank at the end of the event, effectively erasing their materiality. In this scenario, demolition and disassembly represent more than a simple material reversal of the construction process. Because it is an expected state of mind from the outset, material loss is not followed with dread or grieving. Rather, it is a pleasurable social activity that encourages detachment. As a result, the spiritual value of the festivities, and hence the value to be preserved, is equal parts tangible assembly product and destruction. Bodies, buildings, and cityscapes all take on new meanings and looks. The city is revived, and it is depicted as a flexible urban condition - not a grand vision, but a "grand adjustment."

Source: 5 <https://www.architectural-review.com/essays/the-indian-city-kinetic-consuming-reinterpreting-and-recycling-spaces>

Figure 9 - Street during festival

Source: 6 <https://www.architectural-review.com/essays/the-indian-city-kinetic-consuming-reinterpreting-and-recycling-spaces>

2.6.5 Kumbh Mela, Prayagraj

The Kumbh Mela is the world's largest religious gathering and ephemeral city, occurring every three years in four different locations. Every 12 years, it takes place in Allahabad, bringing together people from all over the world to bathe in the holy waters of the Sangam (where the sacred rivers Ganges and Yamuna converge with a third mythical river, the Saraswati). For 54 days, the floodplains are transformed into a fully functional holy city, replicating all of the functions of a permanent one. Roads, pontoon bridges, social infrastructure, and tents of various sizes are constructed on the ground, resulting in a patchwork carpet of cotton, plastic, plywood, and other textures, which is organised by a sophisticated infrastructural grid of roads, electricity, and waste management. Approximately seven million people reside in the city throughout its entire existence, with an additional 10 to 20 million visitors during the peak bathing days. Based on previous versions, negotiations between institutions and residents determine the grid and land allocation, leaving the internal organisation of the camps to each community. Material components are small and light enough to be handled and dispersed swiftly and efficiently across the city, making building, reconstruction, and disassembly and reabsorption easier. Every 12 years, a comparable city emerges, exhibiting in its formal design power mechanisms, hierarchical organisation, and relational linkages between old and new citizens. By imitating previous iterations of itself but leaving little traces upon expiry, this massive and remarkable activity generates both urban shape and value.

Figure 10 - Flood plain before Kumbh Mela

Source: 7 <https://pl.cleanplanet.one/article/6-sposobow-na-zrownowazone-wyburzanie-budynkow>

Figure 11 - Flood plain during Kumbh Mela

Source: 8 <https://pl.cleanplanet.one/article/6-sposobow-na-zrownowazone-wyburzanie-budynkow>

Chapter - 3 Site Selection and Site context

3.1 Site Selection

Initially 6 site has been identified.

1. Bhadra Plaza
2. Manek Chowk
3. Ratan Pol
4. Muncicipal Market
5. Law Garden Market
6. Happy Street

Latter on 2 sites has been selected Bhadra plaza and Manek chowk. Manek Chowk and Bhadra Plaza has been selected because the activities that are taking place are more dynamic as compared to other 4 places. Another reason to select these sites is design interventions has been taken at Bhadra plaza and Manek Chowk is not designed. It helps to understand that how design interventions accommodate various types of activities and how organically developed place respond to the activities that taken place.

Ratan Pol

Bhadra Plaza

Manek Chowk

Law Garden Maket

Happy Street

Municipal Market

3.2 Context of Ahmedabad

The city of Ahmedabad was founded in 1411 by Sultan Ahmed Shah. Ahmed Shah, the city's founder, named it after himself. Ahmed Shah created the city primarily for political reasons. The city's location was near an existing Asha Palli commercial hamlet and along former trade routes. As a result, the population remained

business-oriented, and the trading industry thrived. The city's indigenous financial and mercantile elite have shaped the city, and the city's future has been dependent on them.

The city's foundation was recognized by the castle, the three gates, the Friday mosque, and the ceremonial route connecting these elements. The rest of the city grew over time. Muslims lived around the citadel, while Hindus lived to the east.

At first, the town grew slowly until Sultan Mohamad Begada took the initiative and formed a decentralised political system. Sultan permitted his commanders to create townships (paras) and collect profits in exchange for his services. The city flourished swiftly as a result of these good practices. The city walls were constructed in 1457 to restrict the city's growth and provide security to its citizens. The city's irregular shape is owing to the subsequent construction of the wall.

The Bhadra Fort was designed to look like a regal fort. It occupied the highest position. It held the highest place. This was completed after the capital was shifted from Patan to Ahmedabad. At the time, there were two squares. One leads from Bhadra Fort to Jama Masjid, while the other leads from Jama Masjid to Rani No Hajiro. It used to be a Royal Square, but today it's a Public Square. The Royal Square hosted sessions in which the king interacted with his subjects. During conflicts, elephants, horses, and armies gathered there.

During the Sultanate time, the Jama Masjid was constructed. Salah, Iftari, and Tarawih were all held during Ramadan. People grew involved and visited on a regular basis. A few stalls were gradually established to serve these folks, and the market flourished from there. At the same period, people began to settle in this area. Construction of pol homes and chowks is underway. To service the people who came to the city for the carnival, shops and stalls selling dal, pulses, vegetables, housewares, and other products were set up. The city's growth migrated from the east Sabarmati River shore to the city's interior, as shown on the map. It even shows that historic structures built during Ahmed Shah's rule were oriented in the same direction.

Figure 13 – Site location and nearby landmarks

Figure 14 - Monumental Axis

Figure 13 - Site Context

3.2.1 About Bhadra Plaza

Bhadra fort - This is where several emperors' palaces were located at different times. The administrative centre for the many rulers' governance of the city/territory.

Bhadra Maidan – Foreground to the Bhadra fort.

Teen Darwaza - The Bhadra complex's main entrance.

A maidan is a common open space in most mediaeval cities in this geopolitical situation. The Persian word 'Maidan' refers to a big open region in or around a city or town. It serves no purpose or serves no political purpose. It's said to have a very ambiguous nature. It's used for a number of large-scale tasks. There were numerous city-level activities.

The king conducts a procession up to the teen darwaza every Friday. Just outside the teen darwaza were the market (regular) streets. Every Friday, merchants with new and innovative products could display their wares at the Shahi maidan. The king would then select his favorite items and greet the trader as he arrived in the city. On the edges of the maidan, the Khas bazaar grew. On Mondays, the maidan-a-shahi was open to women. The merchandise on display would then be geared towards women. Like the monarch and noblemen, the queen would choose and encourage subjects she was passionate about.

In 2008, the Vastushilp foundation and CEPT university collaborated to submit to the AMC the designs, plans, and DPR for the Bhadra plaza restoration project, and Ahmedabad applied to be included on the tentative global heritage list in 2010. The Bhadra rehabilitation project was influenced by JNNURM narratives, World Heritage City narratives, and B V Doshi's ambition to see what a new public space in modern India would look like. The reconstruction of Bhadra Plaza was finished in 2015. This initiative was supported by JNNURM.

3.2.2 About Manek Chowk

Manekchowk is named after the 15th-century saint "Baba Maneknath." He was a well-known saint at the time. Baba intervened and stopped Ahmed Shah from constructing the Bhadra Fort (his capital). Baba Maneknath knitted a mat every day while the fort walls were being built. Every night, he unwrapped that mat. One day, the fort's walls unexpectedly collapsed. When Ahmed Shah found this, he challenged Baba Maneknath to show his prowess by putting himself in a little jar. After that, Ahmed Shah sealed and buried the jar. He was either buried alive or entered samadhi beneath the soil. The city's first part, Manekchowk, is named after him, and the memorial temple is located there.

Manek Chowk is a vibrant urban center in the heart of Ahmedabad with a street market that dates back to the early 15th century. The city's oldest and most important market complex is Manek Chowk. The market sells vegetables and spices in the mornings, gold and jewels in the afternoons, and some of India's most popular cuisines and snacks in the evenings and nights, depending on the time of day (till 2 a.m.). This temporary night market is one of India's largest, with annual commerce of over 3 million rupees (around \$48,000). Other historically noteworthy structures near Manek Chowk. It is one of Ahmedabad's most important cultural and historical landmarks.

Chapter - 4 Data collection tools and techniques

Method Used

For data collection quantitative method used. Majorly, it would be based on observations and user perception. To understand the user's experience semi structured interviews were conducted. Interviewing individuals as well as families and vendor's peasant on the sites.

Forms of Data Collection

Study is based on preliminary data collection however secondary study has also taken into consideration where its required.

Secondary data have been collected in various forms

1. Maps
2. Activity Mapping (Across the different timeframe)
3. Photographs
4. Videos
5. Plan, Section, Elevation
6. Semi-structured interview of users

As part of primary data collection government documents, reports and proposals have been looked into.

Method used for Surveys

Stratified Random Method of sampling was used for sampling. Samples of vendors and users have been taken.

Chapter - 5 Data Analysis

5.1 Static Elements

5.1.1 Buildings

The most typical component of a static element is a building. They are monumental

Figure 16 - Buildings in Manek Chowk

and permanent in nature. They provide as a foundation for Kinetic components

Figure 15 - Buildings in Bhadra Plaza

5.1.2 Building Frontages

Frontages offer visual character to the area as part of the built form. A sense of welcome tends to attract users.

Figure 18 - Building Frontages in Manek Chowk

Figure 17 - Building frontages in Bhadra plaza

5.1.3 Roads & Footpaths

Roads give access and mobility to a location. It usually has a lot of activities spilling over from the buildings. Footpaths frequently serve as a buffer between buildings and roadways. It restricts pedestrian movement and promotes social contact.

Figure 19 - Roads in Manek chowk

Figure 20 - Roads and footpaths in Bhadra plaza

5.1.4 Parking slots

Unauthorized and needless activities on the roads are controlled by parking zones in defined places.

Figure 22 - Informal parking in Manek chowk

Figure 21 - Parking slots

Figure 23- Parking slot in Bhadra plaza

5.1.5 Bus/ Auto stops

Auto and bus stops are located in specified areas to make them conveniently accessible to all users.

There is no bus stop available within 200 -300m from Bhadra plaza. Minimum distance to the Bus stop from Bhadra Plaza 300-400 m. bus stands marked in yellow are not operating.

There is no bus stop available within 500- 800 m from Manek Chowk. Nearest available bus stop from Manek chowk is 800 – 900m. No designated auto stands available at both sites.

Figure 24 - Bus Stops in the vicinity

5.1.6 Landscape

Landscape provides consumers with brief reprieve and adds aesthetic value to the area. Permanent fixtures are typically use

Figure 25 - Trees in Manek Chowk

Figure 26 - Trees in Bhadra Plaza

5.1.6 Signboards & Billboard

Signboards and billboards add aesthetic interest to a location while also serving as a reference or way to find a specific location.

Figure 27 - Billboards in Manek Chowk

Figure 29 - Signboard in Bhadra Plaza

Figure 28 - Billboard in Bhadra Plaza

5.1.7 Existing interaction places

Act as a rest stop for visitors to the site, allowing them to sit and rest while they are

Figure 30 - Pause points in Manek Chowk

Figure 31 - Pause points in Bhadra plaza

5.2 Kinetic Elements

5.2.1 Traffic Pattern and Pedestrian movement

Pedestrian activity on sidewalks, roadways, across streets, plazas, and chowks demonstrate how space works. The most dynamic movement patterns are chaotic and enable interaction in various places. Hawkers who set up shop along the roadside, whether on the outskirts or on the threshold, frequently redefine the space they occupy. When these hawkers take up residence on the sidewalk, they frequently push foot traffic onto the roads, interrupting traffic patterns and causing traffic congestion.

Figure 32 - Place for people for walk in Manek chowk

Figure 33 - Figure 26 - Place for people for walk in Bhadra plaza

5.2.2 Street vendors and hawkers with Temporary vending infrastructure

They have a fixed location. They could be permanent or temporary, but the shop itself is mobile and can be simply moved. When the sun is especially fierce, vendors employ canopies to create a comfortable environment for users and consumers. Vendors can be divided into two groups.

- 1 Typology in Motion
- 2 Typology Immovable

Figure 34 - Street vendors and hawkers with temporary vending infrastructure in Manek chowk

Figure 35 - street vendors and hawkers with temporary vending infrastructure in Bhadra plaza

5.2.3 Human interactions

Human interaction is one of the most important aspects of the kinetic city. Without humans, kinetic becomes meaningless.

Figure 36 - Human interaction in Manek chowk

Figure 37 - Human interaction in Bhadra plaza

5.2.4 Celebration of festivals

During festivals or procession, the area appears to have changed. It provides visual character, with dynamic components virtually taking over from static aspects.

Figure 38 - Celebration of Mahashivratri in Manek chowk

5.3 How marketplace function

5.3.1 Place for people to walk for some leisure

There are many pedestrians in Manek Chowk. People park their cars at the start of the street and walk down to the stalls because there is a limited allocated parking spot. Because the booths are on both sides of the roadway, there is no designated walking route. As a result, the pedestrian uses the vehicular road. Specific walkways are not constructed for the safety of people since design interventions have not been taken. Pedestrian space, on the other hand, is quite restricted. The street is crowded until late at night, and things like people's shoulders rubbing against one other or a car passing very next to them make people uncomfortable.

Throughout the day, there are many pedestrians at Bhadra plaza. Design interventions have been made in Bhadra plaza, and people have access to large walkways. However, it has not been designed as a market area for vendors and hawkers. Vendors encroach on footpaths and highways, disrupting pedestrian mobility. The plaza was originally intended to be a pedestrian plaza; however, the traffic flow prevents pedestrians from walking at their leisure. Because of the population density and unorganized vehicular activity, the crowd becomes more chaotic, making people uncomfortable walking in.

Figure 40 - Place for people to walk in Manek chowk

Figure 39 - Place for people to walk in Bhadra plaza

5.3.2 Physical comfort

The sellers set up temporary buildings to shield themselves from the sun and rain. The sellers cover their stalls and designated seating areas with large pieces of plastic. On the street, a variety of noises may be heard, including merchants calling people to their stalls, people buying various items from hawkers, car noises, and people conversing while eating. High noise levels also diminish comfort in public spaces, making it harder to converse and overhearing other people's conversations.

Figure 42 - Physical comfort in Manek chowk

Figure 41 - Physical comfort in Bhadra plaza

5.3.3 Definition (Human sensitive scale)

In general, the Walled City's public areas are small in scale, with two to three story buildings opening to small and partially enclosed public areas to prevent heat gain in the buildings. These are human-scale areas that have supported public life for millennia; but, in the current environment, they are dominated by automobiles. The square and its environs feature a densely built-up area with a spatially connected roadway and open space arrangement. The open L-shaped area that forms the Manek chowk. One arm of the L is bounded by the tombs of the kings. The Queen's mausoleum and Muhurat Pol form the other arm. Bhadra fort, institutional buildings, religious structures, residential buildings, and stores surround Bhadra square.

The volume of niche positioned in the structural bay width of the Pol' dwellings is the major feature that makes up the street's edge. The street is defined by store stairway cases, plinth extensions, walkways, concrete paving sections, and, most significantly, the signboards of the many shops for traders. The developed edge provides the opportunity for trade and sociability. All of the structures are connected to one another in the style of traditional 'Pol' housing, with no space between them. They offer the square and open area a sense of confinement and containment, as well as a scale and proportion that communicates its public character while also allowing for the presence of visitors on the ground level, since they occupy its usual cone of view.

The skyline, staggered continuous massing façades, and the horizontal control of flora lines, but varying proportions and features of openings and overhangs give the area a vibrant quality.

Figure 43 - Building vs Street Ratio in Manek chowk

Figure 44 - Building vs street ratio in Bhadra plaza

5.3.4 Qualities that engage the eyes

While in public settings, people desire to have fascinating sight lines and perspectives. Manek Chowk and Bhadra Plaza are historic precincts with architecturally significant structures. Due to the absence of great viewpoints, the presence of monuments in Manek chowk is not felt, while monuments in Bhadra plaza do. The views of the Chowk in the current environment are congested and do not reflect the heritage values of the area, it is noticed. At contrast to Manek chowk, heritage buildings in Bhadra plaza are plainly visible and continuous. As a result, fascinating facades have become a valuable asset.

The informal sellers and other street vendors provide opportunities for a wide range of activities. The area is densely packed with strong retail activities and stores, drawing visitors' attention to the boarding and lively frontages of various stores. Food vendors in Manek chowk install temporary plastic hoardings in front of stores at night to draw the attention of people.

Figure 46 – Quality that engages eyes in Manek chowk

Figure 45 - Quality that engages eyes in Bhadra plaza

5.3.5 Transparency

The Walled City's buildings have traditionally had sitting portals known as *otlas*, which are one or more raised steps at the entry to the chehalier or building. These are generally shared by neighboring homes/shops and are utilized as casual seating areas. However, these places are few in Manek Chowk and are reported to be used for commercial purposes. The first section of Manek Chowk's L on the west side, limited by the King's tomb and the Queen's tomb, consists mostly of jeweler's shops on the ground level and stock stores on the first and second floors. The ground-floor stores' shutters and hoardings preserve transparency between the public and private realms. The shutters at Manek Chowk are closed at night, so tourists are not in the dark about what is going on at the street's edge. The large number of vendors and vending structures in Bhadra plaza create transparency concerns for the establishments behind them because they are not readily visible from the road.

Figure 48 - Transparency in Manek chowk

Figure 47 – Transparency in Bhadra plaza

5.3.6 Maintenance

Both areas were cleaned in the early in the morning as part of the place's regular upkeep. Garbage can be spotted among the booths and on the road. As a result, the street is cleaned, and the leftover rubbish is collected early in the morning. Garbage, dust, animal waste, wastewater, and insects make it difficult to appreciate the environment. Effective trash

management might help both areas provide a better experience. Apart from cleaning, heritage structure upkeep is neglected, and heritage buildings are not adequately maintained, resulting in the destruction of valuable cultural structures.

Figure 50 – Maintenance in Manek chowk

Figure 49 - Maintenance in Bhadra plaza

5.3.7 Quality of construction and design

The structures are mostly two- or three-story wood structures that are narrow and deep. The building bays establish a rhythm, and the corresponding floor lines produce a uniformity that gives the impression of a continuous façade. This creates a framework in which many pieces interact to create a dynamic environment.

Some of the structures in the neighborhood are still built in the typical architectural style of the 15th century. Behind the profile of signs and billboards, there is still elegant fenestration, ornamented holdings, timber architecture and articulation, and superb craftsmanship.

Many historic structures have been dismantled and new ones have been constructed over the decade because of several forces. However, the general massing of the built form has not changed, and qualitative characteristics of the open space, such as scale, proportion, degree of enclosure, edge, and so on, have been preserved.

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Figure 52 - Quality that engage eyes in Manek chowk

Figure 51 - Quality that engage eyes in Bhadra plaza

5.4 Temporal Activities

5.4.1 Activity Mapping Throughout the Day

5.4.1.1 Manek Chowk

Place has completely transformed throughout the day; it shows the market place is kinetic. In the morning cows are eating grass and birds are eating grains. By afternoon chowk has been converted into parking slot and vendors also set up the stores. After 7 PM food vendors come up and place has been converted into food market.

Figure 56 - Manek chowk in the Morning

Figure 55 - Manek chowk in the Afternoon

Figure 53 - Manek chowk in the Evening

Figure 54 - Manek chowk at night

Figure 57 - Activities that happening at Manek chowk throughout a day

5.4.2.1 Bhadra Plaza

Activities that taking place on the same place are constant in flux. In the morning vendors comes up with all the items and started putting it up, vehicular flow is higher because vendors come with all the goods. By afternoon, flow of buyers increase and traffic flow decrease and pedestrian flow increase. After 8 PM vendors start packing up the goods and market place goes back to the city.

Figure 58 - Activities that happening at Bhadra plaza throughout a day

Figure 60 - Bhadra plaza in the morning

Figure 59 - Bhadra plaza in the afternoon

Figure 62 - Bhadra plaza in the evening

Figure 61 - Bhadra plaza at night

5.4.2 Detailed Activity Mapping

Two parts of Manek chowk has been taken for detailed mapping as it shows different characteristics. 4 shops from the first part has been taken and it is a small street present in Manek chowk. The second part is Manek chowk and 3 shops has been for detailed study.

Figure 64 - Manek Chowk

Figure 63 - Bhadra Plaza

5.4.2.1 Manek Chowk

5.4.2.1.1 Activities in the morning on the street

Figure 65 - Street in the morning

Figure 66 - Empty street in the morning

Figure 67- Sweepers cleaning the street

Figure 68 - Street section showing characteristics of the street in the afternoon

Street is 5 m wide. During morning cleaning of the street takes place.

5.4.2.1.2 Activities in the afternoon on the street

Figure 70 - Street in the afternoon

Figure 69 - Shopkeepers arranging their shops

Figure 71 - Few people buying things from the shops

Figure 72- Street section showing characteristics of the street in the afternoon

Shop keepers start organizing their shops. Shop expands by 1.5 meters on the road and use for display things on tables.

5.4.2.1.3 Activities in the evening

Figure 75 – Street in the evening

Figure 73 - Buyers buying things from the shops

Figure 74 - Buyers buying things from the shops

Figure 76 - Street section showing characteristics of the street in the evening

Visitors flow increase during evening
Nearly 2-3 m space remains available for pedestrian and buyers stopping by which makes the place crowded.

5.4.2.1.1 Activities in the afternoon in the chowk

Figure 80 - Section showing characteristics of the street in the morning

Figure 77 - Vendors use umbrellas to get protection from harsh sun

Figure 79 - Vendors setup their shops

Vendors start coming in the afternoon and organize their stalls. Umbrella and clothes are used for protection from harsh sunlight. People park vehicles in front of the shops which hinders the pedestrian movement.

5.4.2.1.2 Activities in the afternoon in the chowk

Figure 82 - Manek chowk in the evening

Figure 81 - People parked their vehicles in front of the shops

Figure 84 - Buyers flow increase during evening

Figure 83 - Section showing characteristics of the street in the afternoon

Visitors and vehicular movement increase. Umbrellas are removed which are put-up for the shade.

5.4.2.1.4 Activities at the night in the chowk

Figure 86 - Manek chowk at night

Figure 85 - Chowk convert into a Dining space at night

Figure 87 - Vendors start packing and foods stalls and dining tables coming up

Figure 88 - Section showing characteristics of the street at night

Vendors selling different things start packing and food vendors started coming. Chowk that is used as a market during day time converts into dining place during night.

5.4.2.2 Bhadra Plaza

5.4.2.2.1 Activities in the morning at Bhadra plaza

Figure 89 - Bhadra plaza in the morning

Figure 92 - Section showing characteristics of the plaza in the morning

Figure 90 - Vendors coming with their sealing materials

Figure 91 - Tables stays at the plaza

The vendors come early in the morning, they bring their selling materials in a cart and unload the things. The vending structure like Kahatla, table are kept in that place only.

5.4.2.2.2 Activities in the afternoon at Bhadra plaza

Figure 93 - Bhadra plaza in the afternoon

Figure 96 -Section showing characteristics of the plaza in the afternoon

Figure 94 - Vendors start organizing their shops

Figure 95 - Vendors start organizing their shops

The shopkeeper start unpacking and start to organize the stalls. When the sun comes up they open their umbrella for shade. The vendors are also seen coming up on the footpath which restrict.

5.4.2.2.3 Activities in the afternoon at Bhadra plaza

Figure 97 - Bhadra plaza in the evening

Figure 98 - Section showing characteristics of the plaza in the evening

Figure 99 - Vendors occupy the footpath

Figure 100 - Buyers flow increase during evening

There is a huge increase in the number of visitors in the evening due to which the place gets overcrowded.

5.4.2.2.4 Activities in the night at Bhadra plaza

Figure 101 -Bhadra plaza at night

Figure 103 - Section showing characteristics of Bhadra plaza at night

Figure 102 - Vendors start packing and disassemble their shops

Figure 104 – Few buyers during night

The vendors start packing up at the night and amount of the visitors also decrease.

Chapter - 6 Issues & Recommendations

Issues	Recommendations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Manek chowk during evening and night traffic create congestion. Bhadra plaza was design as a pedestrian only plaza but vehicular movement is occurring throughout the day. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regulate vehicular movement If design for complete pedestrian zones make sure to provide necessary design elements to restrict vehicular movement 	-
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Manek chowk and Bhadra plaza there is mixed vehicular and pedestrian movement happening 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Separate shaded pedestrian path should be given for the ease of movement for pedestrian Trees should be provide as a natural shade for the area 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vendors has to bring their selling materials in the cart and then they have to go back to the home in order to park their cart. In Manek chowk a small designated parking is provided which is not enough to handle heavy visitors flow and poor visibility People tend to park in front of the shops and the large part of chowk is uses as a parking during a day. Parking slot is available in the middle of the site which encourage vehicular movement in the site and creates problems for the pedestrians. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On site provision for parking space for carts Designated parking area should be given which should be visible and design according to the number of visitors. Parking should be located within the proximity but not in the middle of the site. 	-

Issues	Recommendations	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Manek chowk there is no provision for pause points which can be used by visitors as a pause points where they can actually sit and take a brake. In Bhadra plaza designated interaction places are available but majority of them are occupied by the vendors and baggers families. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pause points at certain distance should be provided for the visitors. Function of the provides pause points should be regulated. 	-
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In Manek chowk during the late evening there is a lot rush due to the change in the activity that taking place. It creates conflict between two different activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities should be regulated throughout different time zone 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All vendors have designated spaces but the market places is way more congested and visitors are not able to walk, stand and buy something with peace of mind. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arrangement of vendors should be in such a way that vendors get enough space for display, space for buyers to stop and buy something and place for pedestrian to pass through. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Designated spaces should be given to the vendors A proper space for the visitors to walk to be provides. Designated space for buyers can also be provided 	<p>-</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Activities spill over from the shops and restricted the pedestrian movement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Defined space should be given to the shops that can be utilize as activities like exhibition of the materials and things that take place from the shops are spill over on the roads and footpath. 	

List of Annexure

Annexure 1- Activities that happening at Manek chowk throughout a day

05 AM	Cleaner Cleaning the Place
06 AM	Filling of Water
07 AM	Coal Picker
08 AM	Waste Picker , Paper Picker, Plastic Picker
	Cow Grazing
	Birds eating grains
09 AM	Beginning of the traffic
10 AM	Parking in the central area
11 AM	Opening Shops
12 AM	Hawkers with Umbrella and Carts
01 PM	People Visit the Place
02 PM	Buying and Selling Activities
03 PM	
04 PM	
05 PM	
06 PM	
07 PM	
08 PM	Vendors(who are there from the morning) started packing and start moving away from the area
09 PM	Food Vendors started coming
10 PM	Vehicles starts going from the central area
11 PM	Food stalls and Tables setting up
12 PM	
01 AM	
02 AM	

Annexure 2 - Activities that happening at Bhadra plaza throughout a day

06 AM	Activities in Temple Started Cleaner Cleanup the plaza
07 AM	Opening up of Shops People started coming Vehicular Traffic increase
08 AM	
09 AM	
10 AM	
11 AM	Opening up of food Vendors Reduce Traffic movement
12 AM	
01 PM	
02 PM	A lot of Rush of buyers Buying and selling activities
03 PM	
04 PM	
05 PM	
06 PM	
07 PM	Reduce in Rush of buyers Traffic increase Vendors started packing Close the shops
08 PM	
09 PM	
10 PM	

Annexure 3 - Street in the morning, Manek chowk

Annexure 4 - Street in the afternoon, Manek chowk

Annexure 5 - Street in the evening, Manek chowk

Annexure 6 - Activities in the afternoon in the chowk

Annexure 7 Activities in the evening in the chowk

Annexure 8 - Activities in the night in the chowk

Annexure 8 - Activities in the morning at Bhadra plaza

Annexure 9 - Activities in the afternoon at Bhadra plaza

Annexure 10 - Activities in the evening at Bhadra plaza

Annexure 11 - Activities in the morning at Bhadra plaza

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